

ISic3324

Two dedications to a Caesar by the Annii

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

base

Editor

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Autopsy

2018.07.17 Prag

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

area of bouleuterion, 1983

Coordinates

37.297479, 13.589125

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo, inventory 22522

Physical Description

A small square marble base (a relatively fine off-white marble), intact on all sides, but with part of the upper rim missing on the front face. There is a recessed square depression on the top surface, which is rough-picked within. The sides are roughly finished, but front and back faces are finely finished (and inscribed)

Dimensions

Height 18.6 cm

Width 32.7 cm

Depth 25.4 cm

Layout

Three lines of Latin letters centred on each of front and rear face, first line larger in both cases

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are neatly cut, with short serifs. P is open on both texts, R is closed. Text A has tall I in line three. The primary difference between Text A and Text B is in the technique, with the letters in A having a flat cut, whereas B is engraved with a more elegant 'v-cut' and more elegant interpuncts. It is likely that the two were carved by different stone-masons.

Letter heights:

Line A 1: 37-39 mm

Line A 2: 32-35 mm

Line A 3: 27-33 mm

Line B 1: 35 mm

Line B 2: 30 mm

Line B 3: 27-29 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line A1 to A2: 12 mm

Interlineation line A2 to A3: 11-13 mm

Interlineation line B1-B2: 10 mm

Interlineation line B2-B3: 10 mm

Text

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Publius and Marcus Annii, of the tribe Voturia, (set this up) to the son of Caesar / Publius and Marcus Annii, of the tribe Voturia, (set this up) to Caius Caesar, son of Augustus

Commentary

The exact explanation for this double dedication remains uncertain. Battistoni and Rothenöfer speculate that the possibly earlier inscription of Text A could have been a dedication to Octavian as son of Caesar, but reject this as somewhat unlikely and prefer the hypothesis that both inscriptions are dedications to Caius Caesar, the grandson and adopted son of Augustus, with Text A containing an erroneous first text which fails to use the correct onomastic formula for Caius. The Annii were a significant family in Agrigento, with involvement in the sulphur industry.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645577

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3324. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358191>

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